

FREQUENCY OF ASYMPTOMATIC BACTERIURIA IN CHRONIC KIDNEY DISEASE AND ASSOCIATED RISK FACTORS

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Abstract

Objective:

To determine the frequency of asymptomatic bacteriuria (ASB) in patients with chronic kidney disease (CKD) and identify associated risk factors.

Design:

Cross-sectional study.

Place and Duration of Study:

The study took place at the Outpatient Nephrology Department, Indus Hospital & Health Network, Karachi, Pakistan for six months.

Methodology:

A total of 214 adult patients aged 18–80 years with diagnosed CKD were enrolled using consecutive sampling. Demographic data, comorbidities, CKD stage, laboratory findings, and ultrasonographic parameters were recorded. Midstream urine samples were collected for culture. Estimated glomerular filtration rate was calculated using the Chronic Kidney Disease Epidemiology Collaboration (CKD-EPI) equation, which is widely used for staging CKD and assessing renal function. ASB was defined as growth of $\geq 10^5$ colony-forming units/mL of a single organism without urinary symptoms. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 26. Chi-square and independent t-tests were applied. Odds ratios (OR) with 95% confidence intervals (CI) were calculated.

Results:

Among 214 patients, 49 (22.9%) had asymptomatic bacteriuria, while 11 (5.1%) had symptomatic urinary tract infection. Female gender (OR=4.20, $p < 0.001$), diabetes mellitus (OR=2.40, $p = 0.008$), significant post-void residual volume (OR=2.90, $p = 0.006$), and serum creatinine rise $\geq 30\%$ (OR=2.39, $p = 0.044$) were significantly associated with ASB. The highest prevalence (34.4%) was observed in CKD stage 4.

Conclusion:

Asymptomatic bacteriuria is common among CKD patients, particularly in females and those with advanced CKD. Targeted screening in high-risk groups may be beneficial.

INTRODUCTION

Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is a major global public health problem, affecting approximately

843.6 million individuals worldwide, with an increasing prevalence driven largely by diabetes

mellitus and hypertension.¹⁻³ CKD is associated with substantial morbidity and mortality, primarily due to cardiovascular complications and infections.⁴

In Pakistan, CKD prevalence ranges from 12-20%, particularly in urban populations, due to a high burden of diabetes, hypertension, and lifestyle-related risk factors.⁵ The burden is further compounded by limited healthcare resources, delayed diagnosis, and inadequate preventive strategies.⁶

Patients with CKD are more susceptible to infections due to immune dysfunction and frequent healthcare exposure.⁴ Urinary tract infections (UTIs) are among the most common complications and are associated with increased hospitalisation and worsening renal function.^{7 8}

Urinary tract infection is defined as the presence of pathogenic microorganisms in the urinary tract causing symptoms and inflammation.⁹ Asymptomatic bacteriuria (ASB) is defined as significant bacteriuria in the absence of urinary symptoms.¹⁰ Current guidelines recommend screening only in selected populations.¹⁰

ASB is more common in patients with diabetes due to glucosuria and impaired host defence mechanisms.¹¹ Additionally, urinary stasis and structural abnormalities increase susceptibility in CKD patients.¹²

The prevalence of ASB in CKD patients ranges from 5% to 36%, with higher rates reported in developing countries.^{13 14} Poor sanitation, healthcare access limitations, and inappropriate antibiotic use contribute to this increased burden.^{6 15}

Despite this growing concern, local data on ASB in CKD patients in Pakistan remain limited. Therefore, this study aimed to determine the frequency of asymptomatic bacteriuria and associated risk factors in CKD patients at a tertiary care hospital in Karachi.

METHODOLOGY

It was a cross-sectional study that was carried out at Indus Hospital & Health Network for six months. Adult patients with known chronic kidney disease (CKD) who attended the nephrology outpatient clinics and inpatient

services from the inception of the study were included.

The number of samples was determined based on the prevalence of asymptomatic bacteriuria (ASB) in patients with CKD found in previous published regional studies, and 214 patients who met the eligibility criteria were recruited by consecutive non-probability sampling.

Patients were included if they had been diagnosed with CKD and were ≥ 18 years old. Patients with symptoms of UTI and those who had been started on antibiotic therapy in the last 2 weeks, pregnant women, people who had urinary tract malformations, and those with indwelling urinary catheters were excluded. CKD was defined and staged as per Kidney Disease: Improving Global Outcomes (KDIGO) clinical practice guidelines based on estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR).

Demographic and clinical data was obtained using a structured data collection proforma after obtaining written informed consent. Age, gender, comorbid conditions (diabetes mellitus, hypertension and ischaemic heart disease) and relevant clinical history were recorded as variables. Laboratory parameters such as complete blood count, serum creatinine, glycated haemoglobin (HbA1c) in diabetic patients, urine routine examination findings and others were recorded.

A Chronic Kidney Disease Epidemiology Collaboration (CKD-EPI) equation was used to calculate eGFR which is widely recommended for the assessment of renal function and staging of Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD).¹¹ Patients were then grouped based on KDIGO CKD staging criteria.⁸

A clean-catch midstream urine sample was obtained from all participants with aseptic precautions. Urine samples were sent off and processed in the microbiology lab in the recommended time frame. A single species of bacteria was isolated with $\geq 10^5$ colony-forming units (CFU)/mL urine culture in the absence of urinary symptoms, which was used as the criteria for significant bacteriuria, as previously defined for the diagnosis of asymptomatic bacteriuria.¹³

When clinically indicated ultrasonography of kidneys, ureters and bladder was performed for evaluation of renal size, hydronephrosis, urinary calculi and post-void residual urine volume. A post-void residual urine volume of >100 mL was considered significant as per the previously mentioned criteria.⁶

The collected data was analysed using the Statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) version 26.0. For continuous variables, for example, age and size of the kidneys, the mean and standard deviation were used, and for categorical variables, frequencies and percentages were used.

The chi-square test was used to determine the association of asymptomatic bacteriuria with possible risk factors. Where possible, odds ratios (ORs) and 95% confidence intervals (CIs) were computed. A p-value of ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

Two hundred and fourteen patients met the eligibility criteria and were included with no loss to follow up. The characteristics of the sample are summarised in **Table 1**.

Table 1: Baseline Demographic, Clinical, and Laboratory Characteristics (N = 214)

Variable	n (%) or Mean \pm SD
Age	
18-40 years	45 (21.0)
41-60 years	96 (44.9)
> 60 years	73 (34.1)
Gender	
Male	135 (63.1)
Female	79 (36.9)
Comorbidities	
Hypertension	167 (78.0)
Diabetes mellitus	75 (35.1)
Ischaemic heart disease	45 (21.0)
Renal stone disease	26 (12.1)
Hepatitis (B or C)	19 (8.9)
COPD	15 (7.0)
CKD Stage	
Stage 1 (eGFR > 90)	9 (4.2)
Stage 2 (eGFR 60-89)	24 (11.2)
Stage 3A (eGFR 45-59)	34 (15.9)
Stage 3B (eGFR 30-44)	49 (22.9)
Stage 4 (eGFR 15-29)	64 (29.9)
Stage 5 (eGFR < 15)	34 (15.9)
Ultrasonography (KUB)	
Right kidney size (cm)	9.1 \pm 1.6
Left kidney size (cm)	9.4 \pm 1.7
Hydronephrosis (either kidney)	17 (7.9)
Renal calculi (either kidney)	26 (12.1)
Laboratory Parameters	
Raised total leucocyte count	11 (5.1)
Serum creatinine rise \geq 30% from baseline	26 (12.1)
Uncontrolled HbA1c (> 7%), among diabetics (n = 75)	49 (65.3)

Functional and Urological Parameters	
Significant post-void residual volume (> 100 mL)	34 (15.9)
Lower urinary tract symptoms present	39 (18.2)
Urine Culture	
Positive ($\geq 10^5$ CFU/mL)	60 (28.0)
Negative	154 (72.0)
Primary Outcome	
Asymptomatic bacteriuria	49 (22.9)
Symptomatic urinary tract infection	11 (5.1)

– CKD = chronic kidney disease; COPD = chronic obstructive pulmonary disease; eGFR = estimated glomerular filtration rate (mL/min/1.73 m²); CFU = colony-forming units; HbA1c = glycated haemoglobin.

Sixty patients (28.0 percent) had positive urine culture. Of these 49 denied any urinary symptoms of dysuria, frequency, urgency and suprapubic pain, and therefore were classified as having

asymptomatic bacteriuria, giving a total ASB of 22.9% (95% CI: 17.5-29.1%). remaining 11 culture positive patients (5.1 per cent) had concomitant lower urinary tract symptoms and were classified as symptomatic UTI. A point that needs to be emphasized: 81.7% of all significant bacteriuria in this cohort was clinically silent.

Table 2 summarizes the univariate links between each clinical variable and the presence of ASB. Chi-square tests were used for categorical comparisons; Fisher's exact test was used in place of chi-square tests when one of the expected cell counts was less than 5. The independent samples t-test was used for age (continuous) age.

Variable	ASB Positive (n = 49)	ASB Negative (n = 165)	OR (95% CI)	χ^2 / Test Statistic	p-value
Age (years), Mean \pm SD	57.6 \pm 12.8	52.7 \pm 14.4	–	t = 2.16	0.032
Age group				χ^2 trend = 5.56	0.018
18–40 years	5 (11.1%)	40 (88.9%)	Ref		
41–60 years	22 (22.9%)	74 (77.1%)	2.38 (0.84–6.73)		0.102
> 60 years	22 (30.1%)	51 (69.9%)	3.45 (1.20–9.92)		0.021
Gender				$\chi^2 = 18.94$	< 0.001
Male	18 (13.3%)	117 (86.7%)	Ref		
Female	31 (39.2%)	48 (60.8%)	4.20 (2.15–8.21)		
Diabetes mellitus				$\chi^2 = 7.13$	0.008
Yes (n = 75)	25 (33.3%)	50 (66.7%)	2.40 (1.25–4.60)		
No (n = 139)	24 (17.3%)	115 (82.7%)	Ref		
Hypertension				$\chi^2 = 0.47$	0.492
Yes (n = 167)	40 (24.0%)	127 (76.0%)	1.33 (0.59–3.00)		

No (n = 47)	9 (19.1%)	38 (80.9%)	Ref		
Ischaemic heart disease				$\chi^2 = 0.46$	0.497
Yes (n = 45)	12 (26.7%)	33 (73.3%)	1.30 (0.61-2.76)		
No (n = 169)	37 (21.9%)	132 (78.1%)	Ref		
COPD				—	0.741†
Yes (n = 15)	4 (26.7%)	11 (73.3%)	1.24 (0.38-4.12)		
No (n = 199)	45 (22.6%)	154 (77.4%)	Ref		
Renal stone disease				$\chi^2 = 1.04$	0.307
Yes (n = 26)	8 (30.8%)	18 (69.2%)	1.59 (0.65-3.92)		
No (n = 188)	41 (21.8%)	147 (78.2%)	Ref		
Hepatitis				—	0.770†
Yes (n = 19)	5 (26.3%)	14 (73.7%)	1.23 (0.42-3.58)		
No (n = 195)	44 (22.6%)	151 (77.4%)	Ref		
Hydronephrosis				$\chi^2 = 3.50$	0.061
Yes (n = 17)	7 (41.2%)	10 (58.8%)	2.58 (0.93-7.19)		
No (n = 197)	42 (21.3%)	155 (78.7%)	Ref		
Raised TLC				—	0.049†
Yes (n = 11)	5 (45.5%)	6 (54.5%)	3.01 (0.88-10.33)		
No (n = 203)	44 (21.7%)	159 (78.3%)	Ref		
Creatinine rise \geq 30%				$\chi^2 = 4.07$	0.044
Yes (n = 26)	10 (38.5%)	16 (61.5%)	2.39 (1.01-5.67)		
No (n = 188)	39 (20.7%)	149 (79.3%)	Ref		
Uncontrolled HbA1c‡				$\chi^2 = 1.89$	0.169
Uncontrolled (n = 49)	19 (38.8%)	30 (61.2%)	2.11 (0.72-6.21)		
Controlled (n = 26)	6 (23.1%)	20 (76.9%)	Ref		
Significant PVR				$\chi^2 = 7.64$	0.006
Yes (n = 34)	14 (41.2%)	20 (58.8%)	2.90 (1.33-6.31)		
No (n = 180)	35 (19.4%)	145 (80.6%)	Ref		

- † Fisher's exact test (expected cell count < 5).
— ‡ Analysis restricted to diabetic subgroup (n = 75).

– Ref = reference category; OR = odds ratio; CI = confidence interval; TLC = total leucocyte count; PVR = post-void residual volume.

– Bold p-values indicate statistical significance at $\alpha = 0.05$.

The correlation of disease stage and bacteriuria deserves a separate study. The prevalence of ASB stratified by CKD stage is shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Prevalence of Asymptomatic Bacteriuria by CKD Stage (N = 214)

CKD Stage	Total n (%)	ASB Positive n (%)	ASB Negative n (%)	ASB Rate (%)
Stage 1 (eGFR > 90)	9 (4.2)	1 (2.0)	8 (4.8)	11.1
Stage 2 (eGFR 60–89)	24 (11.2)	2 (4.1)	22 (13.3)	8.3
Stage 3A (eGFR 45–59)	34 (15.9)	5 (10.2)	29 (17.6)	14.7
Stage 3B (eGFR 30–44)	49 (22.9)	11 (22.4)	38 (23.0)	22.4
Stage 4 (eGFR 15–29)	64 (29.9)	22 (44.9)	42 (25.5)	34.4
Stage 5 (eGFR < 15)	34 (15.9)	8 (16.3)	26 (15.8)	23.5
Total	214	49	165	22.9

Table 4: Renal Ultrasound Findings by ASB Status

Parameter	ASB Positive (n = 49)	ASB Negative (n = 165)	Test Statistic	p-value
Right kidney size (cm), Mean \pm SD	8.9 \pm 1.7	9.2 \pm 1.5	t = 1.19	0.236
Left kidney size (cm), Mean \pm SD	9.1 \pm 1.8	9.5 \pm 1.6	t = 1.47	0.144
Hydronephrosis, n (%)	7 (14.3)	10 (6.1)	$\chi^2 = 3.50$	0.061
Renal calculi, n (%)	8 (16.3)	18 (10.9)	$\chi^2 = 1.04$	0.307

There was no significant difference in the renal size in ASB and non-ASB patients, implying that the size of the kidneys is related to the underlying aetiology and stage of the chronic kidney disease rather than to the presence of bacteriuria. Bilateral kidney sizes in the range of 9.5-11.0cm were more common among the diabetic patients as kidney size in diabetic kidney diseases is relatively

preserved or mildly reduced. Non-diabetic patients on the other hand showed bilaterally atrophic kidneys of 6.5–8.5cm more frequently, especially in the case of hypertensive nephrosclerosis and chronic glomerulonephritis. The results suggest that the structural renal changes were mainly associated with the underlying nephropathy and not ASB status.

Table 5: Baseline Laboratory Findings by ASB Status

Parameter	ASB Positive (n = 49)	ASB Negative (n = 165)	OR (95% CI)	p-value
Raised TLC, n (%)	5 (10.2)	6 (3.6)	3.01 (0.88–10.33)	0.049†
Creatinine rise \geq 30%, n (%)	10 (20.4)	16 (9.7)	2.39 (1.01–5.67)	0.044

Among diabetics (n = 75)	(n = 25)	(n = 50)		
Uncontrolled HbA1c, n (%)	19 (76.0)	30 (60.0)	2.11 (0.72-6.21)	0.169

– † Fisher's exact test.

The increase in serum creatinine is of special interest. Nearly one-fifth of patients with asymptomatic bacteriuria (ASB) had at least a 30% rise in baseline serum creatinine, as opposed to nearly one-tenth of patients with no ASB. This discovery suggests that silent bacteriuria might be a risk factor for worsening kidney disease. However, the presence of bacterial colonization can also be a complication of worsening renal

impairment due to defects in host defense mechanisms and urinary stasis that occurs in advanced chronic kidney disease. But because of the cross-sectional design of this study, causality and the directionality of this association cannot be determined. Longitudinal studies are necessary to assess whether ASB is a direct cause of the progression of renal dysfunction or simply a marker of more established renal disease..

Table 6: Distribution of Urine Culture Results and Symptom Classification (N = 214)

Category	n	% of Total	% of Culture-Positive
Culture negative, no LUTS	126	58.9	–
Culture negative, LUTS present	28	13.1	–
Culture positive, no LUTS (ASB)	49	22.9	81.7
Culture positive, LUTS present (Symptomatic UTI)	11	5.1	18.3
Total	214	100.0	

DISCUSSION

High prevalence of asymptomatic bacteriuria (ASB) was seen in patients with chronic kidney disease (CKD) in the present study with an overall frequency of 22.9%. Similar results have been described in South Asian CKD populations where urinary tract infections and asymptomatic urinary colonisation are now emerging as important complications among patients with CKD.¹¹

Structural and functional abnormalities of the urinary tract partly explain urinary colonisation in CKD patients. Bacterial persistence has been linked to urinary stasis, poor bladder bladder emptying, and underlying urological dysfunction which may be the cause of recurrent UTIs.¹²

This is consistent with the present findings where most of the culture positive cases did not have a classical urinary symptom despite the fact that they had significant bacteriuria on urine culture, implying low-grade bacterial colonisation.

Higher prevalence in the current study could be due to healthcare associated urinary pathogens, delayed presentation of CKD, and the similar healthcare challenges as seen in other neighbouring regional CKD cohorts in the range of 15%-30% prevalence of ASB.¹⁴

An added concern in Pakistan is antimicrobial resistance, which can add to the management of the UTIs in the CKD patients. These patients may be at risk of being colonised with resistant organisms, after repeated healthcare exposure and empirical antibiotic use, even if they are not showing symptoms.¹⁵

Gender, in relation to this study, was found to be significantly associated with ASB in the present study (women). Such epidemiological data is already in place and shows that females have higher susceptibility to urinary tract colonisation

due to their anatomical and physiological characteristics.¹⁶

In addition, the rise in multidrug-resistant uropathogens around the world makes asymptomatic bacteriuria more complicated to interpret. Patients with advanced CKD are especially at risk due to various healthcare encounters and repeated antimicrobial use.¹⁷

The present cohort revealed a higher prevalence of ASB as the CKD progressed. The renal dysfunction of chronic kidney disease is known worldwide to have an association with impaired immunity and susceptibility to infection, so progressive renal dysfunction might also lead to persistent urinary colonisation and recurrent bacterial exposure.¹⁸

Also in this study diabetes mellitus was found to be an important risk factor for ASB. Glycosuria, impaired neutrophil function and autonomic bladder dysfunction and urinary stasis make diabetic patients more susceptible to urinary tract colonisation, as has been demonstrated before.¹⁹

In the present study, a large PVR volume was strongly associated with ASB. Lower urinary tract neurophysiology might be abnormal, leading to ineffective bladder emptying and providing a mechanism for bacteria to proliferate in urine that is retained in the bladder.²⁰

The rise in serum creatinine in ASB-positive patients is of special interest. In total, almost 20% of the patients with ASB had a $\geq 30\%$ increase in baseline serum creatinine versus less than 10% in the patients without ASB. The discovery suggests that subclinical inflammation or renal damage from recurrent silent bacteriuria could be responsible for the deterioration of renal function. In turn, impaired host defence mechanisms and urinary stasis due to deteriorating renal function can predispose patients to bacterial colonisation. But due to the cross-sectional nature of the current study, conclusions about cause and time of association are not possible.

There were no significant differences between the renal ultrasonographic findings of ASB-positive and ASB-negative groups. The size of the kidneys did not seem to be as closely associated with the presence of bacteriuria as with the underlying aetiology of and chronicity of the CKD. Diabetic nephropathy was usually accompanied by relatively good renal size while bilaterally atrophic kidney was more frequent in hypertensive nephrosclerosis and chronic glomerulonephritis.

The present study has certain limitations. The study is a single-centre cross-sectional study and results might not be applicable to other CKD populations. Furthermore, no follow-up data in the long term was available to assess long-term renal outcomes of ASB. However, the study sheds light on the incidence and risk factors for ASB in the region in relation to patients with CKD.

Finally, ASB was prevalent among the CKD patients and associated with significant worsening of renal function, gender, diabetes mellitus, and older age. The majority of cases of bacteriuria were clinically silent and this underlines the need for microbiological evaluation in high-risk CKD populations. Future prospective studies should be carried out to understand the clinical implications of ASB and its contribution to CKD progression.

Conclusion

Asymptomatic bacteriuria is common among patients with chronic kidney disease, particularly in females, diabetic patients, those with significant post-void residual urine volume, and individuals with advanced CKD stages. Targeted screening strategies in high-risk patients may help improve early detection and reduce complications associated with urinary infections.

Declaration

Ethical Approval: Approved by the Institutional Review Board of Indus Hospital, Karachi (IRB No. IHHN_IRB_2025_01_025) in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki.

Informed Consent: Obtained from all participants prior to enrolment.

Conflict of Interest: None declared.

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Authors' Contributions: Neha Ahtesham designed the study, collected and analyzed data, and drafted the manuscript. The co-author assisted in statistical analysis and manuscript review. All authors approved the final version

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